

THE CONCEPT OF DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE PROCESSES IN PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION IN PEDAGOGICAL THEORY AND PRACTICE

Yakubova Feruza Yusufovna

Researcher,

Samarkand State Architectural – construction Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7703585>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th February 2023

Accepted: 06th March 2023

Online: 07th March 2023

KEY WORDS

Development, innovative processes, pedagogical education, development, innovative processes, science, society, economy, production, industry, special character, creative person.

ABSTRACT

In a developing and changing world, the state of national education systems has become a central element of global competition, which requires constant updating of technologies, rapid adoption of innovations, and rapid adaptation to the needs and demands of a dynamically changing world. This situation is determined by the fact that education, being an important factor for maintaining the country's competitiveness and a necessary condition for the formation of an innovative economy is becoming the most important condition for the dynamic socio-economic development of the society, the condition and guarantee of the well-being and security of the state. Recognizing the fact that in recent years, the traditions and approaches of creating conditions that ensure the quality and (free of charge) access to educational services have been formed in the education of Uzbekistan, it should be noted that the level of development of our country's education does not correspond to the students of the innovative socially oriented development of our country.

The transition to a multi-level education system created the need to fundamentally change the content of state education standards. A modern higher education institution is required to introduce new approaches to teaching that require compliance with the requirements of the state educational standards of higher professional education, which are structured on the basis of a competency-based approach along with fundamentals. It is self-evident that the professional formation of a pedagogue cannot be separated from his personal development, because professional competence, professionalism, skill/mastery, individual creativity, and other such derivatives, general cultural competences as the initial image and fundamental component must be the main factors of his formation [1].

Universal competences are the basic competences that accompany a person throughout his life, on the basis of which he builds his new professional image. In this regard, it is important to identify the general cultural competences formed in the educational process, to understand them, and to offer their scientific description/description, to determine the

conditions, methods and technologies that help/contribute to their effective development. Due to the exponential growth of information and the ever-increasing variability/interchangeability of activity technologies, professional competences may not be long-term, while the nature of general cultural competences is stable and unchanging, making a person's thinking flexible, able to learn new things throughout his life, and this is the basis for the professional growth of an individual.

The new priority issues of education necessitated the transition from systematic organization of the educational process to environment-based organization in higher education institutions. In such an organization, the future bachelor's professional, including general cultural competence is formed in the conditions of an educational environment that guarantees his development and independent development.

The concept of development of innovative processes in professional and professional-pedagogical education is widely reflected in pedagogical theory and practice (V.A. Slastyonin, L.S. Podimova, S.Ya. Batishev, E.F. Zeer, N.V. Kuzmina, L. M. Kustov etc.) [2]. The analysis of the studies showed that the development of innovative processes in professional and pedagogical education is related to the development of innovative processes in science, society, economy, production/industry; these processes have a special character and determine the specifics of forming a highly professional creative person capable of effective activity in an innovative environment.

Unfortunately, most of the time, the professional formation of the student takes place without taking into account the characteristics of the educational environment and its components. At a time when it is necessary to focus all efforts on teaching in the context of future professional activity, defining the student as an active subject of knowledge, independent learning and independent development, relying on the subjective experience of students, his individual characteristics, communicative abilities and other aspects, it is still the main the focus is on theory.

In Russia B.N. Bogatyr, V.V. Gusev, V.V. Karpov, M.V. Clarin, N.F. Maslova, M.S. Ivanova and other scientists dealt with the problem of creating an educational environment in HEIs. For example, V.V. Gusev and N.F. Scientists such as Maslova researched the conditions for creating an educational environment based on the integration of social-developing and career-oriented pedagogical technologies that ensure the implementation of cognitive activity of students at various stages of educational activity, that is, the use of the created environment for the benefit of information-targeted management of the formation of the student's personality [3].

We use works in the field of professional competences and competence (V.I. Baydenko, A.S. Belkin, A.A. Verbitsky, I.G. Galyamina, B.N. Guzanov, E.F. Zeer, I.A. Zimnyaya, M.D. Ilyazova, V.A. Kalney, A.K. Markova, T.A. Matveeva, A.Yu. Petrov, Yu.T. Gatur, Y.F. Frolov, A.B. Khutorskoy and others.) These works show the existence of a number of unsolved problems that make it difficult to realize the potential of the higher education environment in the formation of professional competencies on a wide scale, and suggest ways to solve this problem. At the same time, there are almost no special studies dedicated to the study of the educational environment as a factor in the development of general cultural competence of undergraduate students.

The conducted analysis allows to note that there are conflicts between the following in the modern education system:

- transition of higher professional education to the system of personnel training based on steps/levels and insufficient theoretical development of the problem of organizing the environment of higher vocational education system;
- between the need to introduce a competency-based approach to higher school practice on a large scale and the lack of a relevant/adequate model of student's universal competence formation;
- Between the potential of the HEI environment to form general cultural competence of future undergraduates and insufficient reliance on the integrative conditions and resources of the innovative educational environment of the HEI in the pre-vocational/vocational education process.

At the same time, it is self-evident that the need to train dedicated pedagogues aimed not only at professional independent development and solving practical problems, but also at personal development and general cultural competence aimed at productive professional interaction of educational subjects. In this case, it is important to make a transition from the systematic educational process to the environment-based organization paradigm of the integrated educational process in this design activity. At the same time, an integrated approach is required, which includes the entire set of conditions for the development of an innovative educational environment (technological, socio-cultural, informational components of the educational process; educational quality control (management) system, monitoring of the educational process, etc.), in mass practice and scientific researches, mainly the development of directions for the development of the educational environment in the sense of technologicalization of the educational process is observed [4].

Discursive competence is the ability to perceive various types of discourses, which allows building a behavior strategy and background context in the process of professional communication. The formation of lexical competence allows you to meaningfully form a vocabulary, fill it with a variety of terms in the framework of professional activities [5].

Multicultural competence is conditioned by a person's experience of mastering the cultural space, education/education/literacy, upbringing and development, aimed at using cultural standards as criteria for evaluating activities in solving problems of a knowledge, worldview, life and professional nature, ensuring the unity of general and pedagogical culture, is a professionally significant integrative quality that determines the ability to successfully engage in professional, socio-cultural and intercultural activities and to behave harmoniously in a wide range of life and professional situations.

The innovative educational environment of the institutions is a multi-dimensional social-cultural-pedagogical event/phenomenon, a special/specially organized space of the institutions, which supports the activities of teachers and students on mastering professions with all the diversity of their relationships with the surrounding world, the development of all subjects of education and independent includes a collection/complex of innovative educational technologies that help in the development, has a multi-national impact on the formation of professional, including general cultural competence of future specialists, the development of their personal and professional goals/base/orientations, within the

framework of mastering the professional education program and motivation in future/subsequent professional activities /activates incentives and personal potentials/competencies.

The integrative model of the formation of the general cultural competence of a bachelor in an innovative educational environment is built on the unity of purposeful, organizational-technological, assessment-result blocks that ensure the success of the development of general cultural competences and is built on the principles of scientificity, activity-oriented, systematic, integrative, demonstrative, individualization, based on competence, axiological, synergetic, social-pedagogical, educational-methodical approaches, and: organizational-pedagogical, educational-methodical, technological and psychological basic pedagogical conditions are implemented. Projecting the author's model into the educational environment of higher educational institutions involves the implementation of innovative management of the pedagogical process, technologicalization of the educational process, modular teaching, design and interactive technologies, teaching using multimedia and other educational technologies, and the mechanisms of involving students in the educational process as subjects of educational and personal-professional interaction. will be effective only on condition of doing.

Objective criteria, evaluation indicators and assessment mechanisms, which served as the basis for evaluating the formation of general cultural competence of students at different stages of education, as indicators, evaluate general cultural competence as knowledge, skills and abilities, internal mental states and characteristics of a person, his readiness to carry out productive professional activities and this consists of a set of diagnostic tools that take into account the single complex system of the ability to perform actions/movements/works necessary for the integrative model of the formation of the general cultural competence of a bachelor in an innovative educational environment is built on the unity of purposeful, organizational-technological, assessment-result blocks that ensure the success of the development of general cultural competences and is built on the principles of scientificity, activity-oriented, systematic, integrative, demonstrative, individualization, based on competence, axiological, synergetic, social-pedagogical, educational-methodical approaches, and organizational-pedagogical, educational-methodical, technological and psychological basic pedagogical conditions are implemented [4].

Projecting the author's model into the educational environment of higher educational institutions involve the implementation of innovative management of the pedagogical process, technologicalization of the educational process, modular teaching, design and interactive technologies, teaching using multimedia and other educational technologies, and the mechanisms of involving students in the educational process as subjects of educational and personal-professional interaction.

References:

1. Levites D.G. The practice of teaching modern educational technologies. - M., 2018.
2. Piskunov A.I. Reader on the history of foreign pedagogy. - M., 2021.
3. Prokopiev I.I., Mikhalkovich N.V. Pedagogy. - Mn., 2012.
4. Selevko G.K. Modern educational technologies. - M., 2008.

5. Yakubova F.Y. The importance of improving professional vocabulary. "Экономика и социум" №2 (81) 2021. www.iupr.ru